

Assessment of Personal Protective Equipment's (PPES), Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) among Abattoir Workers in Sokoto Ultra-Modern Abattoir, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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The aim of the research is to conduct an assessment through administering a questionnaire on the knowledge, attitudes and practice (KAP) among abattoirs workers on the importance of personnel protective equipment (PPE's) during meat handling and processing. There is a gap in the critical knowledge, attitude and practices of proper waste hygiene among the stakeholders in the livestock processing industry. Besides, there is little history of the implementation of formal and informal education awareness program on meat handling and processing procedures. A lack of awareness, technical knowledge, legislation, practice and strategies are major issues between abattoir workers in most under developed countries .Food contamination from raw meat is an important cause of food-borne disease outbreaks or food poisoning due to improper meat handling and practice by abattoir workers. Therefore, the need for carrying out assessment of Knowledge, attitude and Practice (KAP) among abattoirs workers on the importance of Personal protective Equipments (PPEs) in Sokoto Abattoir.

Key words: Abattoir, Personal, Protective, Equipments, Questionnaire

INTRODUCTION

Increasing quantities of wastes are generated all over the world and slaughterhouses are one of the industries that contribute to these wastes. Waste generation is one of the major impacts of the increasing slaughter rate of food

animals as a result of the growing demand for animal protein. As reported, per capita meat consumption in developing countries has increased threefold with the rising demand leading to increased livestock populations (FAO, 2010) and hence increased wastes generation from their slaughter. Although slaughterhouse wastes could be of potential benefits, they are a major source of public health and environmental hazards if they are not

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properly managed. Their adverse impacts on access to safe water, environmental sustainability, sanitation and human health which are focal points of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) are issues of concern.

The negative impacts of poor slaughterhouse waste management on surface waters as well as underground waters (Ezeohaa and Ugwuishiwu, 2011) are not far-fetched. Contaminations of water bodies by slaughterhouse wastes have been reported to constitute significant environmental and public health hazards (World Bank, 1998; Coker *et al.*, 2001; Nafarnda *et al.*, 2006; Osibanjo and Adie, 2007). The consequences of infection by pathogens originating from poor slaughterhouse waste management can range from temporary morbidity to mortality, especially in high-risk individuals (Nafarnda *et al.*, 2012). Besides, reduced life expectancy in most developing countries especially in sub-Saharan Africa has been associated with inadequate and hazardous waste management, among other factors (WHO, 2005). Despite the fact that the international food management agencies have already provided guidelines to member countries about safe handling procedures such as HACCP and Good Manufacturing Practices (Ali *et al.*, 2010), the knowledge and perceptions of meat handlers on safe food handling in most developing countries particularly Nigeria remain largely unknown. Most studies (Hedberg *et al.*, 2006; Isara & Isah, 2009) conducted were based on food handlers in the restaurants, processed food establishments without any documented report on meat handlers; whereas, cases of food poisoning due to contaminated meat have been on the rise in recent years (Hedberg *et al.*, 2006).

Food and water-borne diseases are widespread in many countries, especially the developing ones. Epidemiological studies have shown that a great proportion of these diseases occur as result of poor food sanitation and unhygienic handling of foods in restaurants and other eating outlets (Antoria, 2002).

Food safety concerns are magnified when an outlet prepares foods from raw materials, since food service workers and personnel have a major responsibility concerning the safety of the food and their actions can affect the health of many people (Byran, 1992). Types of foods that are mostly involved in outbreaks of food-borne diseases include milk and milk products, vegetables, salads and puddings, and meat and meat products (WHO, 2005). Introduction of a HACCP system would improve and reduce the incidence of food poisoning in restaurants and hence facilitate inspection and quality assurance follows up by regulatory authorities. Additionally, introduction of HACCP system may promote international trade by increasing confidence in food safety and provide a more specific and critical approach to the control microbiological hazards in foods than that provided by traditional inspection and quality control approaches (Amref, 1982).

While waste management is a major challenge in urban areas throughout the world (Hwa, 2007), the developing countries are the worst hit given the deficient waste management programmes, which characterize the regions (Yáñez *et al.*, 2002). A lack of awareness, technical knowledge, legislation, policies, and strategies are major issues for waste management in most developing countries (Hwa, 2007). Though there are other sources of wastes in Nigeria, the slaughterhouse as an important component of the livestock industry generates enormous and potentially hazardous wastes. Despite this, there is a gap in the critical knowledge and practices of proper waste management among the stakeholders in the livestock processing industry. Besides, there is little history of the implementation of formal and informal community environmental education awareness programmes on waste management (Ehrampoush and Baghianimoghadam, 2005).

Worse still, there is no waste management programme for the wastes generated from slaughterhouses in most developing countries particularly Nigeria. Adequate knowledge and practice of proper waste management are of tremendous significance considering the aforementioned hazards related to slaughterhouse wastes coupled with other life limiting factors ravaging the developing countries. Food safety is very important for restaurants (WHO, 2005). Once a restaurant is implicated in a food-borne illness, it can result in damaging of its publicity, consumer interest and trust loss, as well as community health regulation and legal charges (McMahon, 2013). Considering the significance of food safety, it is astonishing how there are few studies that examine the awareness of workers of food safety at restaurants. Even though food safety complications can arise during any part of food production, restaurants are a crucial final step in the series "from the farm to fork" (McMahon, 2013).

Such contaminations often occur when food that does not require cooking such as salad is prepared on the same chopping board that has been used to prepare raw meat without adequate washing (Abdul-Mutalib *et al.*, 2012). Cross-contamination can also occur when raw meat is stored above ready-to-eat meals. Thus, separating raw and cooked food and using safe raw materials are some of the five main keys to safer food as developed by the World Health Organization (World Health Organization, 2007). On the other hand, however, the potential contaminating effects from meat can be limited with proper handling by the meat handlers. As reported, food handlers are a major cause of food contamination (Campos *et al.*, 2015).

Food-borne disease outbreaks reported in the United States for instance were associated with mishandling, with 79% from commercial or institutional establishments and 20% from homes (Haapala & Probart, 2004). Another report indicated the presence of *Escherichia coli* and

Staphylococcus aureus on the hands of food handlers (Lues & Tonder, 2007) while multidrug resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* has been isolated from meat being sold for human consumption (Waters, 2011).

Problem Statement

- a. Globally, many studies have shown an increase in the occurrence of food borne pathogens during meat handling and processing.
- b. In Nigeria butchers or abattoir workers adopts a traditional ways of meat handling and processing without proper knowledge and based standard global practice.
- c. Sokoto state is one of the leading livestock producers in the country, and there are few or limited data and study regarding meat handling and processing.

There is a gap in the critical knowledge, attitude and practices of proper waste hygiene among the stakeholders in the livestock processing industry. Besides, there is little history of the implementation of formal and informal education awareness program on meat handling and processing procedures.

A lack of awareness, technical knowledge, legislation, practice and strategies are major issues between abattoir workers in most under developed countries. Food contamination from raw meat is an important cause of food-borne disease outbreaks or food poisoning due to improper meat handling and practice by abattoir workers. Therefore, the need for carrying out assessment of Knowledge, attitude and Practice (KAP) among abattoirs workers on the importance of Personal protective Equipments (PPEs) in Sokoto Abattoir.

Research Questions

- a. What is the level of Knowledge, attitude and practice on meat handling and processing among abattoir workers?
- b. What are the current practices of meat handling and processing in Sokoto abattoir?
- c. What are the risk factors associated with the contamination of meat during processing and handling?

The objectives of this study were to determine the Knowledge, attitude and practice on meat handling and processing among abattoir workers, to evaluate the current practice of meat handling and processing in Sokoto abattoir and to ascertain the risk factors associated with the contamination of meat during processing and handling.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Sokoto state is located to the extreme Northwest of

Nigeria between longitudes 4° 8'E and 6° 54'E and latitudes 12°N and 13° 58'N. It has an estimated population of more than 4.2 million. Sokoto forms boundaries with the Republic of Niger to the North, Kebbi state to the west and southwest and Zamfara state to the east. The state is divided into 23 Local Government Areas (LGA). Farming is the main stay of the state's economy accounting for a significant proportion of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and responsible for about 70% of the total employment. Sokoto state ranks second in the nation's livestock population, with estimated 3 million cattle, 3 million sheep, 5 million goats and 46000 camels. The study was conducted at Sokoto ultra-Modern Abattoir, Sokoto North Local Government, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The abattoir is the only one in the state and receives animals from markets all over the state, neighboring states as well as Niger republic. It was estimated that 139 cattle, over 120 sheep and goats and 12 camels are slaughtered per day. The abattoir is owned by Sokoto State government and managed by Ministry of Animal Health and Fisheries Development, Sokoto, Sokoto State. The state government deployed Veterinarians, animal health superintendents in the abattoir who are in charge of meat inspection in the abattoir, local government staff, these include; Community health workers, animal health scientist and cleaners/laborers.

Commercial Activities in Sokoto

Cattle are one of the major components of livestock existing in Sokoto State. Aside being multiplied and sold to generate income, it has wider usage thus, help in the production of beef, hide and skin, Agricultural manure as well as source of transport for the movement of agricultural products from one location to the other. Similarly, it helps to provide power for the tilling of soil. Cattle are also fattened and sold, cross-breed to improved carcass weight, produce Agricultural manure. It also serves as a source of milk and cheese. The bones and blood are also used as part of ingredients needed for the production of chicken feeds among others. The socio-economic characteristics of cattle farmers in the study area is essential in order to answer the question as to whether they are to adopt and sustain livestock farming in their efforts to ensure food security and income generation (Ishaya *et al.*, 2018).

STUDY DESIGN

A cross-sectional descriptive study was carried out. A structured questionnaire was administered based on knowledge, attitude and practice and through direct observations of the hygienic status and practices by abattoir workers. The target population consists of all the people working in abattoir. Individual verbal consent was obtained from the respondents prior to data collection.

Questionnaire Administration

A self-administered questionnaire for this study was prepared, which consists of four (4) parts; the first part to collect information about the socio demographic features of the respondents consisting (age, marital status, years of working experience, and educational level) the second part will consists of question covering the aspects of practices including (hand washing, wearing of protective cloth (PPEs), cleaning of protective cloth, method of pest control, methods of meat preservation and storage), the third part will cover the aspect of knowledge that involves(training and frequency of the training) and the last part consists of attitude of the respondents toward hygiene that include agree (hygiene is part of their responsibilities, frequency of training can improve hygiene, agree improper storage might be harmful to health and their response on wearing of protective cloth can reduce the risks of diseases).

The questionnaire was designed in English. On an average 15minutes would be spent to interview each respondent. A pre-test of the questionnaire was carried out after which some of the questions were modified in order to improve validity and reliability of the tool.

Number of Questionnaire to be administered

Based on the record, Sokoto Modern Abattoir has a total of one hundred and sixty six ($n=166$) (Ministry of Animal Health and Fisheries Development, Sokoto) workers consisting of fifty six ($n=56$) Veterinarians, Meat inspectors, Environmental Health Assistance (EHA) and Admin staffs, others includes regular one hundred ($n=100$) butchers, and ten ($n=10$) hide and skin workers. In view of this, a total one hundred and sixty six ($n=166$) was administered.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. Descriptive statistics such as means and frequencies was used to present the proportion of knowledge, attitude and practice of hygiene among workers and correspondence analysis in charts and tables. *Chi-square* test was used to test association of the level of education of abattoir workers influenced the frequency of cleanliness and hygiene of protective clothing. Statistical significance was assessed using *p-values* and all results were considered significant if $p \leq 0.05$. The odds ratios (OR) was reported with the 95% confidence intervals (CI).

RESULTS

The aim of the study is to evaluate the level of

knowledge, attitude and practice among abattoir workers and to examine relationship between knowledge, attitude and practice regarding hygiene in abattoir. Personal and general hygiene, training of the abattoir workers, method of pest control and methods of meat preservation and storage were included in this study.

DISCUSSION

Food safety is a significant public health concern in the world. Foodborne diseases due to microbiological agents, including pathogens and biotoxins, and chemical contaminants in food represent serious threats to the health of thousands of millions of people (FAO and WHO, 2003). According to WHO contaminated food contributed to 1.5 billion cases of diarrhea in children each year, resulting in more than 3 million premature deaths (DeWaal and Robert, 2005).

Worker mishandling of food is one of the major causes of food borne disease outbreaks (WHO, 2000). In a study in Ethiopia, Haileselassie *et al.*, (2013) revealed that there was a reasonable gap on food safety knowledge by abattoir and butcher shop workers. Each year, unsafe food makes at least 2 billion people ill worldwide, or about one third of the global population (National Institute for Allergies and Infectious Diseases, 2007). There are more than 250 known food-borne diseases caused by bacteria, viruses or parasites (National Institute for Allergies and Infectious Diseases, 2007). The maintenance of proper hygiene and adequate sanitary conditions is paramount in any meat-processing plant. About 21.1% against 76.5% of the workers agreed they received training when the need arises. But according to Soultos *et al* (2010) regular training of meat handlers regarding the basic concepts and requirements of personal hygiene plays an integral part in ensuring safe products to the consumer.

Many factors have been attributed to the increasing incidence of food borne diseases including population growth, changes in food preparation habits, a rise in the number of food-service establishments, increased consumption of food outside the home and lack of food safety training and education among consumers and food handlers (Motarjemi and Kaferstein, 1999). Worker mishandling of food is one of the major causes of food borne disease outbreaks (WHO, 2000).

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Figure 3.1: Map of Nigeria showing Sokoto State

Table 4.1: Demographic characteristics of the respondent

SN	Characteristics	Variable	N (%)
1.	Age	<20 years	32 (19.3)
		*21-30 years	60 (36.1)
		31-40 years	52 (31.3)
		>50 years	22 (13.3)
2.	Marital status	Single	61 (36.7)
		*Married	94 (56.6)
		Divorce	11 (6.6)
		Widow	0
3.	Level of education	Primary	38 (22.9)
		Secondary	43 (25.9)
		Tertiary	16 (9.6)
		*Non formal education	69 (41.6)
4.	Working experience	<10 years	61 (36.7)
		*11-15 years	64 (38.6)
		16-30 Ears	26 (15.7)
		>30 years	15 (9)
5.	Type of services rendered in the abattoir	Admin staff	8 (4.8)
		*Bleeders	45 (27.1)
		Flaying	30 (18.1)
		Public health duty	15 (9)
		Evisceration	41 (24.7)
		Splitting	27 (16.3)

NB: * Highest proportion

Figure 4.1: Demographic characteristics of the respondent based on age group

Figure 4.2: Characteristics of the respondent based on marital status

Figure 4.3: Characteristics of the respondent based on level of education

Figure 4.4: Characteristics of the respondent based on years of experience

Figure 4.5: Characteristics of the respondent based on type of services rendered

slaughterhouse workers, all 166 questionnaires were available for analysis giving a response rate of 100%. Out of these, workers consisting of fifty six (n=56) Veterinarians, Meat inspectors, Environmental Health Assistance (EHA) and Admin staffs, others includes regular one hundred (n= 100) butchers, and ten (n=10) hide and skin workers. Based on age group, those within 21-30 years were the majority (36.1%) (Figure 4.1), 56.6% were married (Figure 4.2), 41.6% had no formal education (Figure 4.3), and 38.6% had working experience of 11-15years (Figure 4.4) and in terms of services rendered in the abattoir, 27.1% are bleeders which constitutes the highest proportion of the demographic (Figure 4.5).

Age was found to be statistically significantly associated with knowledge of meat hygiene, where the older meat handlers (21-30 years' experience) have better knowledge of meat hygiene than their younger colleagues (< 20 years). This is similar to the findings of a study by Olumakaiye and Bakare, 2013 who found out that older food handlers had better knowledge and practice of food hygiene compared to their younger

colleagues (Olumakaiye & Bakare, 2013) but contrary to the findings of a study in Ibadan, Southwest Nigeria, where the younger meat handlers had more knowledge of food hygiene as they are likely more willing to learn than the older ones (Adesokan & Raji, 2014).

A statistically significant difference was also found between their years of experience as meat handlers and the respondents' knowledge of meat hygiene. Respondents who had spent longer time on the job as meat handlers with a mean length of 19.43 years \pm 11.26 SD had better knowledge of meat hygiene than those whose years of experience was 12.38 years \pm 10.19 SD.

Length of experience as meat handlers was found to improve knowledge of meat hygiene and safety, so experienced meat handlers can train the beginners with few years of experience on meat hygiene. This study shows that 40.4% of the respondents wash their clothes every day after the work. Sneed et al showed that if food handlers take serious note on the cleanliness of their hand, body, and clothing, this will help in preventing incidence of cross-contamination from occurring. (Sneed et al., 2014). Approximately, 84.9% of the respondents

Table 4.2: Practices regarding hand hygiene, pest control, method of meat preservation and storage of the workers in the abattoir.

SN	Characteristics	Variables	N (%)
1.	Hand washing before the work	*All time	119 (71.7)
		Sometime	38 (22.9)
		Not at all	9 (5.4)
2.	Hand washing after the work	*All time	102 (61.4)
		Sometime	41 (24.7)
		Detergent and water	23 (13.9)
3.	Method of hand washing	*Warm water and detergent	118 (71.1)
		Not at all	40 (24.1)
		No idea	8 (4.8)
4.	Pest control	*Yes	98 (59)
		No	55(33.1)
		No idea	13 (7.8)
5.	Method of pest control	*Chemical	88 (53)
		Biological	52 (31.3)
		No idea	26 (15.7)
6.	Method of meat storage	Room Temperature	11 (6.6)
		Cool room	14 (8.4)
		*Refrigerator	141 (84.9)
7.	Method of meat preservation	Smoking	2 (1.2)
		Salting	2 (1.2)
		*Refrigeration	162 (97.6)
		*Frequently	103 (62)
		Not frequently	44 (26.5)
		No idea	19 (11.4)
9.	Disinfection of the slaughter house after usage	*Frequently	80 (48.2)
		Not frequently	75 (45.2)
		No idea	11 (6.6)
10.	Separation of different species of animals slaughtered	*Frequently	79 (47.6)
		Not frequently	76 (45.8)
		No idea	11 (6.6)

*Variables with highest proportion

used refrigerator as means of meat storage. This study finding also revealed that, there is an association between level of education and frequency of the cleanliness of protective cloths ($P < 0.05$) According to Askarian *et al* (2004) there is no difference between the staff who attended an educational course with those who did not. (Askarian *et al.*, 2014). This was supported by several studies and indicates that although training may increase the knowledge of food safety; this does not always produce a positive change in food handling attitude. Food-borne diseases present a serious threat to public health. Such diseases are due to the consumption of food contaminated with microorganisms or their toxins (Hugas and Tsigarida, 2008). Zoonotic diseases are not only transmissible to humans through contact with animal body fluids but also through the ingestion of contaminated meat (Norrung and Buncic, 2008). The incidence and prevalence of food-borne diseases can be reduced significantly if food handler's knowledge, attitude and practices were improved. Roberts and de Jager (2004) described abattoir as one of the food industries that contribute to the problem of food-borne diseases and potential health hazards associated with food unless

the principle of food hygiene is implemented.

In this study, it was observed that almost all (97.6%) of the respondents refrigerate the processed meat. Improper temperature in meat processing and storage allows for growth and rapid proliferation of microorganisms which cause food-borne diseases (Adams, 2014). The study conducted by Bas *et al.* also agrees with poor usage of refrigerator for food preservation due to lack of knowledge of correct refrigerating temperature (Junaidu *et al.*, 2014). Although the respondents in this study showed reasonable knowledge (84.9%) of refrigeration being a means of preventing microbial growth and spoilage of meat, their poor implementation may be due to the quantity being processed at the abattoir for sale since the eventual preservation of the meat has been transferred to the end consumer or whoever buys the meat from them. The proportion of them that reflected in the use of refrigeration is likely to be the meat handlers who process reasonable quantity that exceeds daily sales which has to be stored before eventual stock is sold. Lack of adequate cold room or refrigerating facilities could also be the cause for this poor practice.

Figure 4.6: Characteristics of the respondent based on method of storage

Figure 4.7: Characteristics of the respondent based on practice regarding hygiene (washing of hand)

Respondents who are older and had spent longer time on the job as meat handlers had good practice of meat hygiene than those who were younger and had spent shorter time on the job. Since age and length of experience as meat handlers were found to improve the practice of meat hygiene and safety, older and experienced meat handlers can train the younger ones with few years of experience on meat hygiene. Respondents' knowledge of meat hygiene is also associated with their practice of meat hygiene. This is corroborated in this work owing to lack of awareness on the part of meat handlers on the routine hygienic practices required in their work place. Marriot (1999) reported that poor food hygiene practices can contribute to outbreaks of food borne illnesses. For the achievement of improved food safety for consumers, abattoir personnel and environment including compound and

surroundings need to be cleaned on regular basis. In terms of practices regarding hand hygiene, pest control, method of meat preservation and storage of the workers in the abattoir, respondents that wash hand all the time constitutes a greater proportion (71.7%). Also, 61.4% of the abattoir workers do wash hand after the work and 71.1% uses warm water and detergent for washing hand. Nel et al., 2004 suggested that soap and hot water at 45°C should always be available at the washing basins for meat handler's use.

The use of paper towel sheets rather than fabric cloths, dish towel or apron for hand cleaning should be encouraged as micro-organisms can easily accumulate on such materials (Marriot, 1999). Majority of the respondents ($n=119$, 71.7%) are washing hand all the time before the work, using gloves during food preparation as well as proper cleaning and handling and

Figure 4.8: Practice by the abattoir workers based on hand washing technique

Figure 4.9: Practice regarding method applied during meat storage

Figure 4.10: Practice regarding method applied during meat preservation

Figure 4.11: Practice by the abattoir workers regarding pest control

Figure 4.12: Practice by the meat handlers regarding pest control techniques

preparation instruments reduce the risk of food contamination. Pest control is very vital in the abattoir operations, 59% and 53% of the respondent control and applied chemicals for pest respectively (Figure 4.11). In terms of meat storage, 84.9% stored meat in refrigerator and 97.6% preserved meat in the same process (refrigeration). (Figure 4.9 and Figure 4.10) Sixty two percent (62%) of the respondent frequently wash off

inside drains (Figure 4.13), 48.2% disinfects slaughter house after usage and 47.6% separate different species of animals slaughtered during handling and meat processing (Figure 4.14)

In relations to practices regarding nature of personal protective equipment's and method of cleaning of instrument of the workers, the highest proportion among the characteristics variables includes workers working

Figure 4.13: Practice by the meat handlers regarding washing of offal in drains

Figure 4.14: Practice regarding disinfection of the slaughter house after operation

with apron 51.2%, those that doesn't have hand gloves 62.7% those with absence of boot and facemask account to 51.8% and 53.6% respectively (Figure 14.5)

Also, 40.4% workers clean their protective clothing on daily basis and 23.5% applied water as a cheap method of cleaning the instrument (Figure 14.7). Since the purpose of wearing overalls is to protect both the food and the meat handler from cross-contamination, overalls suitable to wear over other clothing (Nel et al., 2004).

Morrone and Rathbun (2003) indicated that risks along the food chain can be minimized through educate consumers and workers on food safety. Without the

knowledge of food safety practices and food handling procedures, food borne illnesses cannot be reduced. Redmond and Griffith (2003) reported that to ensure this, there should be some form of introductory training with regular updating and refresher courses for food handling. Meat handlers must also understand the risks associated with food contamination by microbiological agents, and should be able to prevent meat contamination (Adams and Moss, 1997).

Educational levels and training of meat handlers regarding basic concepts of meat safety and personal hygiene plays a vital role in ensuring that the consumers

Table 4.3: Practices regarding nature of protective clothing, cleaning of the cloth and method of cleaning of instrument of the workers in the abattoir.

SN	Characteristics	Variables	N (%)
1.	Nature of protective clothing	*Presence of Apron	85 (51.2)
		Absence of Apron	74 (44.6)
		No idea	7 (4.2)
		Presence of hand gloves	59 (35.5)
		*Absence of hand gloves	104 (62.7)
		No idea	3 (1.8)
		Presence of boot	79 (47.6)
		*Absence of boot	86 (51.8)
		No idea	1 (0.6)
		Presence of face mask	76 (45.8)
2.	Cleaning of the protective cloth	*Absence of face mask	89 (53.6)
		No idea	1 (0.6)
		*Daily	67 (40.4)
		Twice a week	46 (27.7)
		Once a week	28 (16.9)
3.	Method of cleaning of instrument	Irregular	25 (15.1)
		Only water	39 (23.5)
		*Water and detergent	110 (66.3)
		Warm water	17 (10.2)

*Variable with the highest proportion.

Figure 4.15: Practice regarding the use and nature of protective clothing

are provided with safe and wholesome products (Jianu and Golet, 2014). On the knowledge of workers regarding training and frequency towards hygiene of training in the abattoir operations, 76.5% did not obtain any training regarding hygiene, 87.3% and 60.8% received twice a year and once a month respectively (**Table 4.4 and Figure 4.18**). Cross-contamination is the result of bacteria being transferred from a source, raw meat, work surfaces or equipment to the ready-to-eat food (Engel and MacDonald, 2001). Bacteria can be transferred directly,

whereby the source touches the ready-to-eat food or indirectly through a worktop or an individual's hand. Ignorance, poor design and poor food handling by staff are some of the reasons why indirect contamination occurs (Engel and MacDonald, 2001).

On general hygiene perception, the respondents indicated that the slaughter slabs were washed daily after slaughter, a highly welcome routine procedure, although there is need for the slabs to be washed every morning before slaughter because animal food is always

Figure 4.16: Practice on cleaning of protective clothing

Figure 4.17: Practice based on the method of cleaning instruments.

Table 4.4: Knowledge of workers regarding training and frequency towards hygiene of training in the abattoir

Characteristics	Variables	Scores	N (%)
Receive any training regarding hygiene	When the need arise?	Yes	35 (21.1)
		No	*127 (76.5)
		No idea	4 (2.4)
	Twice a year?	Yes	17 (10.2)
		No	*145 (87.3)
		No idea	4 (2.4)
	Once in a month?	Yes	19 (11.4)
		No	*101 (60.8)
		No idea	46 (27.7)

*Scores with the highest proportion

Figure 4.18: Knowledge of workers regarding training and frequency towards hygiene of training in the abattoir

microbiologically contaminated by organisms living naturally or entering from surroundings or through operational procedures (Lewicki, 1993). In addition to this, regular updating and refresher courses should be carried on more frequently. This will help the meat handlers to have a better understanding of risks associated with contamination of food with microbiological pathogens and sanitation practices (McIntyre *et al.*, 2013)

Categories on the attitude of workers regarding training and frequency towards hygiene of training in the abattoir, the finding reveals that 84.3% stated that hygiene is part of their responsibilities. 88.6% indicated that the use of protective clothing can reduce the risk of diseases. 90.4%

highlighted the need for frequent training in improving hygiene of the workers during meat handling and processing. Moreover, 87.3% of the workers stressed that improper handling and storage might be detrimental (**Table 4.5 and Figure 4.19**). There is need for proper arrangement for health service delivery for abattoir workers considering the hazards associated with meat handling. The importance and advantage of having an on-site health services or clinics especially in large food handling establishment with large work force has been emphasized (Hobbs and Roberts, 1993).

Food-borne diseases cause economic and social problems such as loss of income, loss of man power and medical care costs, For instance, Salmonellosis is

Table 4.5: Attitude of workers regarding training and frequency towards hygiene of training in the abattoir

Characteristics	Variable	Scores	N (%)
Attitude of workers of hygiene	Hygiene is part of their responsibilities?	*Yes	140 (84.3)
		No	20 (12)
		No idea	6 (3.6)
	Protective clothing can reduce the risk of diseases?	*Yes	147 (88.6)
		No	14 (8.4)
		No idea	5 (3)
	Frequent training can improve hygiene on workers?	*Yes	150 (90.4)
		No	9 (5.4)
		No idea	7 (4.2)
	Improper handling and storage might be harmful?	*Yes	145 (87.3)
		No	15 (9)
		No idea	6 (3.6)

*Variable with the highest scores

Figure 4.19: Attitude of workers regarding training and frequency towards hygiene of training in the abattoir

estimated to cost the United States between 1613 and 5053 million dollars annually (Van der Heijden *et al.*, 1999). The human body is a reservoir for numerous microorganisms with hands being the main agents for cross-contamination with food handling establishment (Gordon-Davis, 1998; Muinde and Kuria, 2005); it is important that all possible measures be taken to reduce or eliminate such contamination (Muinde and Kuria, 2005). Gordon-Davis further explained that during food handling, disease causing micro-organisms may be transferred from a food handler's body to the food. In abattoir operation; certain prerequisite programmes have

to be considered to provide basic environmental and operating conditions that are necessary for production of safe food (Lawan *et al.*, 2013).

These prerequisite programmes include good manufacturing practices, good hygiene practices and standard operating system (Declan *et al.*, 2004). For public health purposes, an abattoir has been defined as a premise approved and registered by the controlling authority for hygienic slaughtering and inspection of animals, processing and effective preservation and storage of meat products for human consumption (Alonge, 1991; Codex Alimentarius, 1993). The slaughter

practices in an abattoir contribute significantly to the keeping quality of meat both in the abattoir and in the retail outlets. The purpose of an abattoir is to produce hygienically prepared meat by the humane handling of the animal using hygienic techniques for slaughtering and dressing (FAO, 1992).

Hygiene problems are not limited to slaughtering but are also associated with incorrect processing, marketing and other practices (Akinro *et al.*, 2009). Good hygienic state of the abattoir or slaughter house is therefore very necessary to eliminate likely zoonotic microorganisms and make the quality of meat presented for sale and consumption reasonably healthy. Foods prepared without following hygiene rules result primarily in food poisoning and many other diseases that have negative effects on human health (Sanlier and Turkman, 2010). Due to the fact that disease outbreaks often lead to economic losses, food handler training is an important business strategy for managing food safety risks. Food handler training according to Smith, (1994) is seen as one strategy by which food safety can be increased, offering long-term benefits for the industry. The general hygiene in the abattoir will encompass the sanitary state of the environment within which the slaughter takes place and within which the staff operate, the house, equipment and other facilities such as toilets and baths.

The personnel hygiene comprises the quality of staff members and other casual workers in the abattoir. It includes their health, hygiene and habits. Personnel hygiene is defined by John (1991) as clean as is reasonably practical of hands, forearms, neck, hair, and any clothing liable to come into contact with food. This study was carried out to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of the meat handlers regarding personal and general hygiene so as to ascertain the need for training with regards to hygiene and general of management of the abattoir. Among the respondents, 66.3% also use water and detergent frequently as a method of cleaning of instrument is readily available in the abattoir and equipment such as knives were washed after slaughter. All the respondents claimed that they would like an improvement in the hygienic state of the abattoir. Alonge (1991) defined meat hygiene as a system of principles designed to ensure that meat and products are safe, wholesome and processed in a hygienic manner fit for human consumption. The deplorable state of our abattoir and poor personal hygiene of meat handlers have been associated with food borne disease outbreaks. Attala and Kassem (2011) stated that bacteriological quality of meat products is strongly influenced by the prevailing hygienic condition during their production and handling.

The perception on training of the meat handlers regarding hygiene, 76.5% indicated the need as mandatory not when the need arises as shown by 21.1% of respondents hence expressed interest to be trained by

government as self-sponsored training may be unaffordable (Table 4.4). Adams and Moss (1997) reported that training of food handlers regarding the basic concepts and requirements of personal hygiene plays an integral part in ensuring safe products to consumers. In our abattoirs, butchers and meat handlers are self-employed people and may not be able to sacrifice their meager resources for training. Government either at the local or state level may have to be involved if not wholly but by subsidizing the cost. Such training should be carried out from time to time and with inducement if need be. Standard of practice habits have been linked with management attitudes towards training (Tebutt, 1992). Gnomes-Neves *et al.*, (2011) conducted a survey on the knowledge of practice of 159 meat handlers in slaughter slabs in Portugal and posited that although majority of these candidates had achieved professional training, further training was deemed necessary. The study advised that such training should have a strong knowledge practice connection and considered motivation factors. Previous research found that food safety training increased knowledge regarding food safety issues (Lynch *et al.*, 2003). Training and education may be an effective tool to increase food safety knowledge and awareness of hygiene among food handlers and thus improve food safety practices (Gillespie *et al.*, 2000). There is a need to have sufficient knowledge of food safety and be able to apply such knowledge during food preparation (Mortlock *et al.*, 1999).

Thus, transferring knowledge into areas of food handling practices is of priority concern and it is clear that much more have to be discovered about food handlers' attitudes toward food safety issues as well as their potential to influence practices (Ko, 2013). Green *et al.* (2007), however, mentioned that training itself was not sufficient to ensure that handlers perform this procedure properly. Some knowledge did not necessarily results in the applied the correct techniques because of the workplace barriers (Clayton and Griffith, 2004; Green *et al.*, 2006) from the work staff, including inhibitory attitudes of supervisors and colleagues, time pressures and/or lack of staff, as well as structural factors, such as facilities and accessibility to supplies causing food handlers to prioritize other activities that they perceive as having more importance.

Demographic characteristics of respondents

From this study reflected that majority of the workers in all categories are male (84%) with the remaining manned by women. These findings were contrary with other studies that were conducted in Brazil (Hanashiro *et al.*, 2005) and in Thailand (Cuprasitrit *et al.*, 2011). Regarding to the level of education attained most of slaughterhouse workers and meat sellers had no formal

education (such as Tsangaya). It indicated that they were not well educated but they learnt from their experiences in which 38.6% work for 11-15 years. It was similar studies in developing countries (Abdul-Mutalib *et al.*, 2012; Baş *et al.*, 2006) and even in developed countries (Angelillo *et al.*, 2000; McIntyre *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, it can be seen that respondents worked without specific education and also nearly 50% of pork sellers have never attended in course that related to food safety. Other studied were quite similar to those reported even lower levels of trained food handlers in Nigeria (Chukuezi, 2010) and Ghana (Omemu and Aderoju, 2008).

Knowledge of respondents

The result shows the overall knowledge regarding training and frequency towards hygiene of training in the abattoir as relates to food safety. Most of slaughterhouse workers and meat sellers answered correctly in whether they received training regarding hygiene. There are many studies that their participants acquired more correct answers with the questions that are related to maintaining good hygiene (Abdullah Sani and Siow, 2014) and washing of hands (Haapala and Probart, 2004) thus, indicating good knowledge with respect to personal hygiene and knew that washing their hands with only water is enough and no need to use antiseptic or detergent. This is similar observation with study by Bas *et al.* (2006a) performed in Turkey, food handlers had limited knowledge that related to hand hygiene; food handlers agreed that hand washing with mild detergent was sufficient to prevent food contamination. From this study, it showed that most of respondents lacked the knowledge regarding hygiene and frequent training. Training and education may be an effective tool to increase food safety knowledge and awareness of hygiene among food handlers and thus improve food safety practices (Gillespie *et al.*, 2000). There is a need to have sufficient knowledge of food safety and be able to apply such knowledge during food preparation (Mortlock *et al.*, 1999).

Thus, transferring knowledge into areas of food handling practices is of priority concern and it is clear that much more have to be discovered about food handlers' attitudes toward food safety issues as well as their potential to influence practices (Ko, 2013). Green *et al.* (2007), however, mentioned that training itself was not sufficient to ensure that handlers perform this procedure properly. Some knowledge did not necessarily results in the applied the correct techniques because of the workplace barriers (Clayton and Griffith, 2004; Green *et al.*, 2006) from the work staff, including inhibitory attitudes of supervisors and colleagues, time pressures and/or lack of staff, as well as structural factors, such as facilities and accessibility to supplies causing food handlers to prioritize other activities that they perceive as having

more importance. Therefore, the training of food handlers should be carried out covering social, environmental and organizational factors, and with greater focus on risk perception that may lead to unsafe practices (Coleman *et al.*, 2000; Ehiri *et al.*, 1997).

Attitudes of respondents

Apart from the knowledge, attitude is also a crucial factor that may influence food safety behavior and practice, thus decrease the occurrence of Foodborne diseases. Approximately 84.3% of the workers and meat sellers agreed that hygiene is part of their responsibility and handling food safely was important part of their job responsibility and only 3.6% have no idea (**Table 4.5**).

Majority of the respondents reported positive attitudes that, hygiene is part of their responsibilities (84.3%) this is also supported by a previous study in which the respondents (76.9%) stated that hygiene and safe food handling was an important parts of their job responsibilities (Siow and Sani, 2011). Most of them (88.6%) agree that, the use of protective clothes can reduce the risk of diseases and cross contamination. Almost 90.4% agree with statement that frequent training can improve hygiene practices within the abattoir. All of them stated that improper storage of meat might be harmful. However, in the previous study, food handlers might be aware of the food safety attitudes they should have, but 63.0% of their respondents admitted that they seldom practice such positive attitudes. (Raspor, 2008)

According to Zanin *et al.* (2015), almost 51.5% were aware of danger of wearing adornments. Most of the respondents (88.6%) agreed that using protective clothing such as protective gloves and adequate clothing reduce the risk of diseases. This result was similar to the study by (Buccheri *et al.*, 2010) where they have also found that more than 90% of their respondents believed that the used of protective clothing, gloves and proper storage of food stuffs were vitally important in reducing food spoilage and health hazards to consumers.

The statement of slaughterhouse workers with abrasion or cuts on fingers and hands should not be handling foods without gloves was approved by 75.00% in this study. Comparatively, Tokuç *et al.* (2009) found that almost all (93.2%) of their food staffs were aware of the danger in touching food with cut hands or fingers. But the most significant result was from Angelillo *et al.* (2001) who found that 99% of their food staffs did not touch food with cut hand or fingers. This observation is in contrast to those reported by Codex Alimentarius Commission (2003) with the stated that "Sick food handlers who are known or suspected of having any diseases that might be transmitted by food are not allowed to work or deal with foods".

However, in the previous study by Clayton *et al.* (2002), meat handlers might be aware of the food safety attitudes

they should have, but 63.0% of their respondents admitted that they seldom practice such positive attitudes. This proved that although most of the food handlers in this survey gave positive answers but they might not practice it when handling foods. Based on Nee *et al.*, 2000, there were strong correlation between knowledge and food handling practices. Hence, training, motivation and initiative should be provided to encourage food handlers practicing appropriate attitudes and procedures when working in food areas (Nurul Huda 2008).

Practices of respondents

Personal hygienic practices are extremely important to ensure that the food produced is safe for the consumer. Practices regarding nature of protective clothing, cleaning of cloth and method of cleaning of instruments of the workers in the abattoir are vital. In the present study, it was found that slaughterhouse workers have good hand hygiene. All of slaughterhouse workers always wash their hands with detergent before processing meat, this result is similar with meat seller's practices.

According to the Codex Alimentarius Commission (2003), improper food handling was a major cause of food borne diseases and poor hand hygiene was an important risk factor in the occurrence of food contamination. Food handlers should always wash their hands at every stage of food production, particularly before handling foods, after eating, after touching contaminated materials, after using the washroom, etc. Majority of the respondent (51.2%) use apron during operation.

All of them remove the personal stuff such as watches, ring and jewelry that can contaminate foods while working. Similar results were demonstrated by Çakiroğlu and Uçar (2008), 84.2% indicated that they did not wear jewelry during food production. Abdul-Mutalib *et al.* (2012) showed high practice levels of general sanitation measures. Codex Alimentations Commission (2003) stated that sick food handlers who are known or suspected of having any disease that might be transmitted by food are not allowed to work or deal with foods. In this study, only 35.5% uses hand gloves and majority of the respondent (62.7%) doesn't have it, also, 51.8% has rain boot and 53.6% doesn't have a face mask. This percentage was very high that should consider contamination with food. It did not have rules to prohibit them to do their jobs and subsequent meat contamination.

This proved that although most of the abattoir workers in this survey gave positive answers but they might not practice it when handling meat. In Sokoto Ultra-Modern abattoir, there is no clear division of slaughtering process into stunning, slaughtering/bleeding, skinning, evisceration, chilling/hanging, cutting/deboning and

frozen delivery as well as preventive mechanism installed for rodents and insects control. According to Roberts and de Jager, abattoir is one of the food industries that contribute to the problem of possible food-borne diseases and potential health hazards associated with food unless the principles of food hygiene are implemented. (Roberts & Jager, 2004) this fact is also supported by this study finding where there is a gap in the training of the abattoir workers on handling of meat and maintaining hygienic status in their working area, because the training is normally done when there is a particular need. Since the aims of wearing overalls are to protect both the food products and the meat handler from cross contamination, overalls should be suitable to wear over other clothing.

However, this study showed that 44.6% of the abattoir workers did not wear overall and 62.7% do not wear glove they all handled food with their bare hands and handling of foods with bare hands may also result in cross contamination, hence introduce microbes on safe food. Since meat handlers is one of probable sources of contamination for microorganisms, it is important to take all possible measures in order to reduce or eliminate such contamination. (Muinde and Kuria, 2005). However, this study found that, 71.1% of the respondents wash their hands with warm water and detergents. According to World Health Organization (WHO) the effective requirement of hand washing includes washing of hands in hot soapy water before preparing food and after using the bathroom, changing diapers and handling pets (WHO, 2014).

When food handlers did not practice good personnel hygiene or proper handling, they can be the vector for growth of microorganisms through hands, cuts, mouths, skins and hairs (Bryan 1988) According to Bas *et al.* (2004), the staff employed in food and beverages services should have a clean, tidy and proper appearance, without any skin infections, good dental hygiene, have short finger nails and are not in the habit of biting nails, do not wear jewellery except wedding ring, wearing no make-up, work in clean shoes and uniform, and stick to good hygiene practices Angelillo *et al.* (2001) and Askarian *et al.* (2004) stated that using of gloves is mainly influenced by employees' ages where younger workers seem to be more motivated in preventing risk practices compared with older workers In the aspects of food safety, answers provided by the respondents indicated that level of their practices was average, in which the overall percentage was 59.3%. Data for the risk factors showed that majority of the cases were due to improper food handling practices (Clayton *et al.* 2002). A study in USA proposed that inappropriate food handling practices lead to 97.0% of foodborne diseases (Howes *et al.* 1996).

Food-borne diseases have been recognized as a major human health problem occurring commonly in both developed and underdeveloped countries, particularly in

African countries, because of unhygienic handling of food and poor sanitation practices. Lack of adequate food safety laws, weak regulatory systems, insufficient financial resources to invest in safer equipment, and lack of education for food handlers are also major contributors to this problem (Aluko *et al.*, 2014)

Food handlers participate in the final stage of the prevention of foodborne diseases (Sani and Siow, 2014). The hands of food handlers can be vectors for the spread of foodborne diseases because of poor personal hygiene or cross-contamination (Bas *et al.*, 2006a). They must take significant steps to minimize the pathogen contamination to the minimum level in food (Medeiros *et al.*, 2004). Food handlers should have excellent hygiene practice to ensure cross contamination is reduced, thus protecting the consumers from Foodborne diseases (Abdul-Mutalib *et al.*, 2012). To ensure that food handlers have the awareness, knowledge and practice related to the correct way of handling food, training and education are essential parts of their job (Martins *et al.*, 2012).

Numerous studies indicated that training may increase knowledge but does not always result in behavior change (Powell *et al.*, 1997). Incentive factors and hindering factors should be considered for change practice. In contrast to food hygiene training, meat handler training represents one of the most effective strategies to maintain and mitigate food safety risks (Jianu and Golet, 2014). However, these personal hygiene practices are only claims from the respondents and due to the lack of evidence, there is no guarantee they carry out what they stated in the questionnaires, shortcomings observed in the implementation of personal hygiene practices can be addressed by proper training, educating and monitoring of the workers, the study revealed that the respondents had acceptable level of knowledge, excellent attitudes and good practices toward food hygiene measure, but there is a need to increase the level of hygiene in the abattoir premises, and there are gaps identified highlighted the necessity of proper professional training and routine medical examinations of workers coupled with health certificates. Therefore, proper training, monitoring and educating slaughterhouse worker will help to ensure that the consumers and the imported countries to be provided with good quality wholesome meat all the times.

Personal hygiene practices investigated in this study include wearing of protective clothing, the cleaning, and disinfection of working clothes, smoking, eating and drinking at the workplace. These practices are considered as mandatory preventative measures which have to be implemented during the slaughter process to reduce chances of cross contamination (Nel *et al.*, 2004). Wearing of protective clothing is one of the major measures implemented in the food industry. It helps to prevent cross contamination. Protective clothing helps to protect both the food product and the meat handler from

cross contamination (Muinde and Kuria, 2005).

The study showed that the respondents always use a cap and apron these results are in agreement with the results of Van Zyl (1995) who proposed that overalls, hair nets (beard nets, if any), hard hats, rubber boots, and aprons should always be worn by the meat handlers. According to Abd Elaleem *et al.* (2014) hairnets and beard-nets specifically help to prevent loose hairs and also dandruff from falling into the food since hair is reported to be a source of *Staphylococcus aureus*, on the other hand, handling of foods with bare hands may also result in cross contamination; hence introduce microbes on safe food.

The unhygienic and unwholesome practices of hiding infected products increase the risk of selling to the public infected and contaminated meat product. Over time and with repeated meat inspections butchers acquire ample knowledge about the nature of pathologies that can lead to condemnation of carcasses just from observing the activities of the Veterinary staff. Unruly butchers could obstruct inspection of their animal carcasses or hide lesions from unassisted inspectors. Similar findings of Cadmus *et al.*, (2008), in Nigeria, stating that pathological cases including zoonoses in slaughtered animals were missed due to uncooperative attitudes of butchers in ensuring thorough meat inspection

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), "Hygiene refers to conditions and practices that help to maintain health and prevent the spread of diseases. The term "food hygiene" is used to describe the preservation and preparation of foods in a manner that ensures the food is safe for human consumption, and to prevent – as far as possible – the contamination of food. Personal hygiene of food handlers pertains to the hygiene practices that prevent contamination food with mixing chemicals, spreading from people, pets, and pests. Personal hygiene is performed by an individual to care for one's bodily health and wellbeing, through cleanliness. Motivations for personal hygiene practice include reduction of personal illness, healing from personal illness, optimal health, social acceptance and prevention of spread of illness to others. Other practices that are generally considered proper hygiene include washing hands regularly and especially before handling food, washing scalp hair, wearing clean clothing, cutting finger nails. Moreover, it is an important factor to be aware of dangers of cross contamination between raw and cooked food by separate raw and cooked food. Temperature and length of time should appropriate for cooking. Food handlers store food at the proper temperature.

Apart from slaughterhouses, it should be consider transportation and cleaning and management of processing meat in market. Therefore, in further study should include the microbiological indicator in the step of transportation. Apart from training programs should be provided, there is a need to better understanding about

cross contamination problem in meat production chain and government should realize the real problem and cooperate with stakeholders to find the techniques or solve problems. Overall, majority of the respondents (71.70%) had good knowledge of meat hygiene. Hand washing practices of the respondents (95.28%) are similar with the findings of the study conducted by Haapala and Probart (Haapala & Probart, 2004).

The majority (91%) of the meat handlers in Jiggiga abattoir and retail meat shop in Ethiopia knew that regular washing of hands before and during meat processing reduces risk of contamination (Tegegne & Phyo, 2017). Similar findings reported in the study conducted by Sani and Siow also show that 92% of the respondents had good knowledge of hand washing before handling or processing food (Sani & Siow, 2014). This is important since hand washing plays a vital role in altering the channel or route of disease transmission via food or meat contamination. Meat handlers should maintain this habit and also improve on other important hygienic procedures to avoid meat contamination (Ansari-Lari *et al.*, 2010).

Another issue of concern from this study is the poor knowledge on sources of meat contamination by respondents. This may probably be due to the inadequate regular and consistent training for the meat handler as majority of the respondents in this study were of the opinion that professional training could help improve good practices in food industry. It is important to put in place certain interventions such as regular update training to close the knowledge gap. Washing hands by food handlers during processing is considered as one key important hygiene practice to prevent cross contamination (Assefa *et al.*, 2015). All respondents from the Assefas study (Assefa *et al.*, 2015) indicated that they always wash and properly sanitize their hands before starting the slaughter process. Our results contradict reports by a number of authors from other places in the world where hand washing and sanitization was found to be inadequate (Jianu, 2014; Abd-Elaleem *et al.*, 2014).

CONCLUSION

The study revealed there is high level of knowledge, attitude and practice of hygiene among abattoir workers, but there is a need to increase the level of hygiene in the abattoir premises. It also shows that workers with good attitude have a better practice but knowledge is not necessarily associated, however there is need to increase the level of knowledge on hygiene practices among abattoir workers in order to reduce the incidence of diseases and sickness in state. The study contributes to the understanding of the current situation in one of the most important abattoirs in Sokoto and the related public health risks, indicating the need for improved facilities

and formal training on food safety and sanitation in order to improve meat safety at the abattoir.

It appears from the present research work that KAP study of food handlers in general and that of meat handlers in particular is just a step towards understanding their views. Other strategies including psychological factors that affect their behaviour and practices should be explored. Generally, the knowledge, attitude, and practice of meat hygiene is good, but these would require sustained improvement through training and capacity building on meat hygiene, consistent stakeholders engagement, mentorship of younger meat handlers by the older ones, and regular public health and meat hygiene education by the veterinary public health practitioners.

This study provides a framework for future policy formulation on food safety improvement that would cascade or transcend to better public health. The study shows that there is reasonably good knowledge, which reflected in the good practices of meat hygiene. The attitude of the respondents, however, is not associated with these knowledge and practice, as revealed by the study. In general, the meat handlers displayed a reasonable knowledge and practice of meat hygiene although there is still need for improvement on the hygiene practices in the abattoirs. The study further reveals that the older people, meat handlers who are married, and meat handlers who have spent longer years on the job have better knowledge and practice of meat hygiene than the younger ones.

RECOMMENDATION

Proper training, monitoring and educating slaughter personnel will help to assure that the consumers are provided with good quality wholesome meat all the times. Further research is recommended to validate the workers' knowledge and general practices through microbiological correlation of meat samples to these practices. Routine inspections by responsible authorities are also advisable to assess compliance with the standards and requirements according to the rules and regulations for safer meat processing in abattoirs.

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